

DAMAGE EVALUATION OF Ti/GFRP LAMINATES UNDER LOW-ENERGY IMPACT LOADING

H. Nakatani, T. Kosaka, J. Oki, K. Osaka and Y. Sawada
Graduate School of Engineering, Osaka City University
Osaka, 558-8585, Japan
d07ta001@ex.media.osaka-cu.ac.jp

SUMMARY

In the present paper, the impact responses and overall damages of fibre-metal laminates based on Ti alloy and GFRP were investigated. From the experimental results, it was found that the interlaminar delaminated area in GFRP layer increased sharply with the initiation of single crack in Ti layer. The FE models were able to simulate the impact responses and the delamination growth behaviour in GFRP layer.

Keywords: Fibre-Metal Laminates, Ti/CFRP, Impact, Impact damages, Damage evaluation and simulation

INTRODUCTION

Fibre-Metal Laminates (FMLs) are the hybrid materials that consist of thin layers of metal and fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP), and have excellent fatigue resistances and damage tolerances. FMLs have been applied to several aircrafts, for instance, ARALL (aluminium alloy/aramid fibre) were applied to the cargo door of C-17 military transport, and the upper fuselage of Airbus A380 was made of GLARE (aluminum alloy/glass fibre) so far [1-2]. In recent years, investigations of Ti/CFRP laminates (a.k.a. TiGr) as FMLs have been increasing, and these laminates are thought to be promising materials that withstand the severe environment of advanced supersonic aircrafts that require operating temperature as high as 177°C (350°F).

Many works that deal with the impact properties of these FMLs have already been presented. Vlot [3] examined the damage behaviour and the dent depth after impact of ARALL and GLARE. Laliberte [4] presented the impact damage characterization of GLARE. Bernhardt [5] characterized the impact response of TiGr by two failure modes. Cortés [6] revealed the energy-absorbing mechanisms during impact of TiGr. However, in these works, overall size and extent of the internal damages were not evaluated sufficiently since these internal damages were evaluated using cross-sectional images because titanium alloy layers as face sheets and CFRP plies make it difficult to observe internal ones. In addition, the relationships between damages observed and impact responses of the laminates were not explained, and the impact analysis model presented by Seo [7] is not considered to present actual damages as well.

In the present paper, in order to observe the overall damages and to reveal the relationship between these damages and impact responses under impact loading as Ti/FRP laminate system, low-energy impact tests were conducted on Ti/GFRP

laminates and damages after impact were observed in detail. By using GFRP as FRP layer, internal damages were easily identified due to the transparency of this material. Furthermore, finite element models based on the damages observed were suggested, and the interactions between internal/external damages and impact responses of the laminates were evaluated.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Ti/GFRP laminates examined in this work were manufactured by bonding Ti alloy sheets (Ti-6Al-4V, $t:140\mu\text{m}$) to both faces of the cross-plyed GFRP laminates (GF/epoxy prepregs, CW tapes:GE352G135SBEZQWS, Mitsubishi Rayon Co., LTD.) using epoxy adhesive (DP-460, Sumitomo 3M LTD.). The mechanical properties of these constituent materials obtained by static tensile tests (0.5mm/min. at room temperature) were tabulated in Table 1. Specimens applied to the impact loading were cross-plyed GFRP laminates and Ti/GFRP laminates, and their stacking sequence were $[0_4/90_4]_s$ and $[\text{Ti}/0_3/90_3]_s$, respectively. These two laminates were almost the same in thickness (1.6 to 1.8mm).

Low-energy impact tests were conducted by using a drop-weight tower with a pneumatic rebound brake system. A spherical impactor made of steel with 10mm in diameter was used and impactor mass was 2kg. Impact velocity and impact energy were calculated from the drop height of the impactor. The square specimens with a size of $100\times 100\text{mm}^2$ were clamped by two steel panels with central opening with diameter of 80mm and fixed by also using epoxy adhesive (Araldite, Huntsman).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Impact Responses and Damages of Ti/GFRP Laminates

The extent of damage in GFRP layer of Ti/GFRP laminates was compared to that of GFRP laminates. Damage aspects from the impact direction after impact loadings with impact energy of 7.84J were shown in Fig.1. The GFRP layer of the Ti/GFRP laminates were observed after the upper titanium layer was physically removed. From this figure, it was found that the interlaminar delamination and matrix cracks of Ti/GFRP laminates were reduced by the stiffening effect of titanium and adhesive layer. Figure 2 shows the interlaminar delaminated area in GFRP layer as a function of impact energy. The delaminated area in GFRP laminates increased continuously with the impact energy. On

Table 1 Material properties of Ti alloy sheet, epoxy adhesive and unidirectional GFRP plate.

	t [mm]	E [GPa]	ν	σ_y [MPa]		
Titanium	0.14	85.9	0.380	826		
Adhesive	0.20	1.62	0.384	27.5		
GFRP UD one layer	t [mm]	E_{11} [GPa]	E_{22} [GPa]	ν_{12}	G_{12} [GPa]	G_{23} [GPa]
	0.101	36.9	10.0	0.32	3.30	3.60

Fig.1 Impact damages in GFRP layer with impact energy of 7.84J.

Fig.2 Interlaminar delamination area vs. impact energy of cross-ply GFRP and Ti/GFRP laminates.

the other hand, there was a “jump” of delaminated area of Ti/GFRP laminates at about impact energy of 4.8J. In the following section, the impact responses and damages of Ti/GFRP laminates around this impact energy will be evaluated.

Damage aspects of Ti/GFRP laminates after impact loading with impact energy of 4.70J and 4.90J were photographed in Fig.3. With the impact energy of 4.70J, convex deformation was given in the titanium layer at opposite side of impact, and the interlaminar delamination in GFRP layer stayed within the area of Ti-GFRP interfacial delamination. However, as the impact energy increased to 4.90J, single crack occurred in titanium layer and the interlaminar delamination in GFRP layer expanded wider than the area of Ti-GFRP interfacial delamination. Figure 4 shows the load-time and load-displacement traces during these impact events. The load response showed a smooth curve because no cracks initiated in the titanium layer with the lower impact energy of 4.70J. With the higher impact energy of 4.90J, single crack occurred in titanium layer and so the load values were fluctuated because the local bending stiffness near the

Fig.3 Impact damages of Ti/GFRP laminates with impact energy of (above) 4.70J and (below) 4.90J. (The titanium layers at the impacted side were removed.)

Fig.4 (a) Load-time curves of Ti/GFRP laminates with impact energy of 4.70J and 4.90J.

Fig.4 (b) Load-displacement curves of Ti/GFRP laminates with impact energy of 4.70J and 4.90J.

impact point decreased with the initiation of the crack in titanium layer. Hence, interlaminar delamination in GFRP layer would widely expand when single crack was presented in the titanium layer at opposite side of impact.

Numerical Model of Impacts for Ti/GFRP Laminates

In order to verify the relationship between the internal/external damages and impact behaviour of Ti/GFRP laminates obtained the previous section, finite element analyses were carried out, and the analytical results were compared to the experimental ones. From the symmetric properties of each damage mode, 1/4 of the laminates were modelled as shown in Fig.5. Figure 6 shows the configuration of each layer and impactor. The used element types for each layer were tabulated in Table 2. The Ti layer and adhesive layer, GFRP layer and the steel impactor were modelled using solid continuum element, shell continuum element and rigid element, respectively. Ti/GFRP laminates were assembled by binding the nodes of adjacent layers. Material constants used in these analyses were the same values given in Table 1. The damages like the crack in Ti layer, Ti-GFRP interfacial delamination were presented by releasing the binding or boundary conditions in actual time based on the experimental results. Hashin failure criteria was also applied for GFRP layer to represent the damage initiation caused by the impact loading. After these criteria were satisfied, damage growth was simulated by stiffness degradation. The strength of unidirectional GFRP plates required by Hashin failure criteria were shown in Table 3. In addition, the cohesive elements were inserted into the $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}$ interlaminar interfaces of the cross-plyed GFRP layer in order to represent the interlaminar delamination. The cohesive behaviour was defined directly in terms of a traction-separation law, and damage was assumed to initiate when a quadratic nominal stress criterion was satisfied. Table 4 shows the parameters for this criterion. The impact loadings were represented by applying the initial velocity to the impactor. In the present paper, two cases of impact velocity (impact energy) of 2.17 m/s (4.70 J) and 2.21 m/s (4.90 J) were applied. As seen in the previous section, there were no cracks in the Ti layer after the impact loading with impact energy of 4.70 J and single crack was presented with impact energy of 4.90 J. The finite element modelling and analyses were carried out by using ABAQUS (Dassault Systèmes).

Fig.5 The finite element model of the Ti/GFRP laminates with the impactor.

Fig.6 Configuration of each layer and impactor.

Table 2 Element types for each part.

Part name	Element type	Element name in ABAQUS
Impactor	Rigid element	R3D4
Titanium alloy layer	Solid element	C3D8R
Adhesive layer	Solid element	C3D8R
GFRP ply	Shell continuum element	SC8R
Layer for the delamination	Cohesive element	COH3D8

Table 3 Parameters for Hashin's failure criteria.

	0° direction	90° direction
Tensile strength [MPa]	820	80.6
Compressive strength [MPa]	500	322
Longitudinal shear strength [MPa]		54.5
Transverse shear strength [MPa]		161

Table 4 Parameters for quadratic nominal stress criterion used in cohesive element.

Nominal stress normal mode [MPa]	Nominal stress 1 direction [MPa]	Nominal stress 2 direction [MPa]
65	57.5	57.5

Figure 7 shows the deformation of elements after dynamic analysis with impact energy of 4.70J. From this figure, it was found that plastic deformation of the titanium layer observed by experiments was also obtained by the finite element analysis. The load-time curves obtained from the dynamic analyses with impact energy of 4.70J and 4.90J were compared to the experimental results in Fig.8. In these figures, the maximum load values and the responses after the maximum load differ slightly from the experimental responses. The possible reason of these results is that the influence of energy dissipation by the friction at the damage area like matrix cracks was not considered in the analyses. However, the overall responses of the laminates with impact damages simulated successfully. With the impact energy of 4.70J, the load values showed smooth response because no crack occurred in the titanium layer at opposite side of impact. On the other hand, initiation of single crack in the titanium layer with 4.90J presented the fluctuation

to the load response. From these results, it was shown that the fracture of the titanium layer contributes to the impact responses of the Ti/GFRP laminates by the finite element analyses as well as the experimental results.

Fig 7 Aspect of the deformation of the elements after the dynamic analysis with impact energy of 4.70J.

Fig.8 (a) Analytical and experimental results of impact responses of Ti/GFRP laminates with impact energy of 4.70J.

Fig.8 (b) Analytical and experimental results of impact responses of Ti/GFRP laminates with impact energy of 4.90J.

In the next step, the finite element analyses with impact energy of 3.92J and 5.88J were also carried out, and then the relation between the impact energy and interlaminar delaminated area in GFRP layer was evaluated. Figure 9 shows the experimental and analytical interlaminar delaminated area in GFRP as a function of applied impact energy. Analytical values were obtained by summing the area of cohesive elements in lower $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interfaces where the quadratic nominal stress criterion was satisfied. In this figure, the “jump” of interlaminar delaminated area near the impact energy of 4.8J was obtained by the finite element analyses as well as experimental results. From these results, it was shown that the crack initiation in the titanium layer at the opposite side of impact caused the growth of interlaminar delamination in GFRP layer.

Fig.9 Analytical and experimental interlaminar delaminated area in GFRP layer of Ti/GFRP laminates as a function of impact energy.

CONCLUSIONS

- (1) Compared to the cross-plyed GFRP laminates, the impact damages like the interlaminar delamination and matrix cracks in Ti/GFRP laminates were constrained because of the stiffness of the titanium and adhesive layer.
- (2) The interlaminar delaminated area in GFRP of Ti/GFRP laminates increased sharply with impact energy of 4.8J or more. And with these impact energies, single crack occurred in the titanium layer at the opposite side of impact.
- (3) The impact responses of the Ti/GFRP laminates with or without the crack in the titanium layer were simulated successfully by the finite element models suggested in this work.
- (4) As the impact load showed fluctuation with the initiation of the crack in titanium layer, the fracture of titanium layer contributes to the impact response of Ti/GFRP laminates.
- (5) The finite element models also showed the sharp increase of the interlaminar delaminated area in GFRP layer by the occurrence of the crack in titanium layer with the impact energy of around 4.8J.

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